

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INVESTIGATING CHOLESTEROL LEVELS IN PLEURAL FLUID IMPLICATIONS FOR DIAGNOSIS OF MALIGNANT PLEURAL EFFUSIONS

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Abstract

Classifying an effusion as exudative or transudative is only the first step in unraveling the complex network of diagnostic challenges that lie beneath the surface of each hydrothorax. The focus is shifted towards applying an approach tailored to each specific case. Personalized assessment is crucial for making an informed decision about which biochemical markers should be tested. A controversial notion in the field of pleural effusions is the potential for pleural fluid to be analyzed for the presence of cholesterol. Its levels, either alone or in relation to those in the blood, further narrow the diagnostic scope and pave the way for an accurate identification of malignant pleural effusions.

In an attempt to clarify the role of cholesterol in the diagnosis of malignant pleural effusions we carried out a one-year-long case-control observational study, which included patients of varying age, clinical manifestation and primary etiology. A total of 151 patients were included in the analysis. The control group consisted of 72 patients, all of whom were diagnosed with benign disease, confirmed by subsequent biopsy. Of these, 38 cases were confirmed as inflammatory, and 34 were verified as pleural effusions of non-inflammatory origin. Malignant pleural involvement was confirmed in 79 patients. These two groups are representative of the main types of pleural pathology.

Keywords: cholesterol, malignant pleural effusion, diagnosis, pleural analysis.

Introduction

Cholesterol is the main sterol in the human body. It is a component of cell membranes, a main structural element of the central nervous system, it participates in steroidogenesis, and many other processes in the human body. Structurally, we differentiate three types: high-density lipoproteins (HDL), low-density lipoproteins (LDL), and very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL). HDL is the primary transporter of cholesterol from various parts of the body to the liver, where its metabolism occurs.

Lipoproteins can enter the pleural fluid as a result of increased vascular permeability or as a product of the cellular metabolism of degenerating cells. On the one hand, mesothelial cells themselves participate in extrahepatic cholesterol synthesis, which is regulated by their metabolic needs and the constantly changing balance of cholesterol delivery from LDL and its removal by HDL [1,2]. This process is aided by the damage to cholesterol-containing leukocytes and erythrocytes in the pleural fluid. Furthermore, increased permeability of the vascular endothelium is a precondition for the entry of plasma cholesterol into the pleural cavity.

For the purpose of differentiating between transudative and exudative pleural effusions, a clinical-laboratory threshold for cholesterol in hydrothorax is accepted at levels >45 mg/dL [3], with elevated levels in exudates being independent of serum sterol levels. Cholesterol levels in pleural effusion are also considered in the context of chylous pleural effusions. In these

cases, cholesterol levels <5.18 mmol/L-1 (<200 mg/dL-1) are observed, along with elevated pleural triglycerides (PF-TRIG) >1.24 mmol/L-1 (>110 mg/dL-1), pleural leukocytosis >1000 cells/mm³ with $>80\%$ lymphocytes [4]. Outside the context of chyloform pleural effusions, increased levels of triglycerides and chylomicrons in pleural fluid are hypothesized in a long-standing hydrothorax, as well as in severe pleural empyema and parapneumonic pleural effusions [5].

Materials and Methods

In order to achieve the stated goals and objectives, a cross-sectional, observational case-control study was conducted in a Bulgarian population of patients with pleural effusions.

The screened male and female participants for this study were recruited from patients hospitalized at the Department of Thoracic Surgery at UMHAT "Kaspela", Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

The choice of statistical methods was made in accordance with the objectives of the study, the type of variables, and established practices in scientific research in the field of thoracic surgery. The systematization, processing, and analysis of primary data were carried out using the IBM SPSS Statistics software package. The analysis and conclusions from the study were derived after a summarized presentation of the empirical results in tabular form. The graphical analysis was conducted using MS Office 365. To clarify the results of the analyses conducted, the following statistical-mathematical methods were used:

Kolmogorov-Smirnov One-Sample test: A non-parametric test used to check whether a given sample follows a specific distribution. It compares the empirical distribution of data with the theoretical distribution.

Independent Samples t-test: A parametric test used to compare the mean values of two independent groups.

Levene’s Test for Equality of Variances: A statistical test used to check for equality of variances between two or more groups.

Results

To analyze whether the pleural cholesterol values follow a normal distribution, we will first apply the Kolmogorov-Smirnov One-Sample test. The results obtained are presented in Table 1. N indicates the number of observations. The mean value is noted as "Mean." Standard Deviation shows the standard deviation, while "Absolute" represents the absolute value or the largest deviation between the empirical and normal curves. "Positive" and "Negative" indicate the direction of the largest deviations from the normal curve.

Table 1

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Tes applied to pleu-ral cholesterol levels

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		holpun
N		151
Normal Parameter s ^{a,b}	Mean	1.7025
	Std. Deviation	0.81446
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.085
	Positive	0.085
	Negative	-0.054
Test Statistic		0.085
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.009 ^c

It is evident that the selected variable significantly deviates from the normal distribution, which is supported by the asymptotic significance, which in all cases is below the standard significance level of $p < 0.05$. Clearly, this variable is not assumed to follow a normal distribution. This hypothesis is further supported by the application of the Independent Samples t-test, which allows us to check if there is a statistically significant difference between the mean values of the relevant variable in the two patient groups.

In this test, Levene's test for Equality of Variances checks whether the variance between the two groups is statistically significant and if the two groups demonstrate homogeneity of variances. The t-test for Equality of Means looks for a difference between the

mean values of the two groups and determines if it is statistically significant. The t represents the value of the t-test, Df is the degrees of freedom, and Sig.(2-tailed) is the p-value, indicating whether the difference between the mean values is statistically significant. Mean Difference is the difference between the mean values of the two groups, while the 95% Confidence Interval of the Difference is the range within which the true difference is expected to be found in 95% of cases.

The results presented in Table 2 are interesting to note as cholesterol levels demonstrate a Levene’s Test (Sig. = 0.165); $t(149) = -2.559$, $p = 0.011$, therefore Levene’s test shows equal variances, but p demonstrates values close to significance.

Table 2

Independent Samples Test applied for pleural cholesterol levels

		Independent Samples Test								
		Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Interval of the	
									Lower	Upper
holpun	Equal variances assumed	1.943	0.165	-2.559	149	0.011	-0.33346	0.13031	-0.59097	-0.07596
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.525	130.635	0.013	-0.33346	0.13206	-0.59472	-0.07220

Discussion

A comprehensive analysis of the available literature establishes that elevated cholesterol levels in pleural fluid are associated with the exudative nature of hy-

drothorax. In a study conducted by Shen and colleagues, pleural cholesterol was linked with high sensitivity (88%) and specificity (96%) for detecting malignant pleural effusions [6]. On the other hand, Mathie

P.G. reported sensitivity, specificity, PPV (positive predictive value), and NPV (negative predictive value) of the method as 75.7%, 98%, 99.1%, and 59.2%, respectively [7]. In an attempt to determine cut-off values for cholesterol in pleural fluid, Guleria suggests a threshold of 60 mg/dL, which, according to their study, provides a sensitivity of 88.2% and specificity of 100%. For comparison, in the same study, using Light's criteria, sensitivity was 98% and specificity 80% [8].

Additionally, Hamm demonstrated that malignant pleural effusions register significantly elevated pleural cholesterol levels, independent of serum cholesterol, with an average value of 94 mg/dL, followed by inflammatory pleural effusions (76 mg/dL) and non-malignant effusions with 30 mg/dL. He also proposed a threshold of 60 mg/dL, which distinguishes exudative from transudative pleural effusions with only a 5% error rate [9].

If we compare these findings with our own results, we observe several points of overlap. Based on the data from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, with $p=0.009$, we can state that the values do not follow a normal distribution. From the test for equality of variances, equal variation in the data is observed, as $p=0.165$. However, the test for equality of means shows a difference between the mean values, with $p=0.011$.

Given our presented results and the available information, we can conclude that pleural cholesterol is one of the best diagnostic tools for aiding in the diagnosis of malignant pleural effusions.

Conclusion

The analysis of pleural cholesterol levels proves to be a valuable diagnostic tool in distinguishing between malignant and non-malignant pleural effusions. Elevated cholesterol levels are consistently associated with exudative effusions, particularly in malignant cases. Studies, such as those by Shen, Mathie, and Hamm, demonstrate high sensitivity and specificity in using pleural cholesterol as a diagnostic marker, with suggested threshold values around 60 mg/dL offering a reliable distinction between exudates and transudates. Our own findings further confirm these patterns, as significant differences were observed between groups, despite equal variances. Therefore, pleural cholesterol should be considered a key parameter in the diagnostic evaluation of pleural effusions, particularly for malignancy detection.

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